

Awareness and Attitude of Consumer Towards Organic Clothing with Special Reference to Coimbatore Retail Outlets

Dr.E.Dhanasekar | Dhakshitha G

Department of Commerce International Business, Dr.N.G.P Arts and Science College (Autonomous), Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu - 641048

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KEYWORDS

Sustainability,
Organic clothing,
Manufacturing method,
Coimbatore retail store,
Purchase decisions,
Sustainable Fashion.

ABSTRACT

Expanding demand in organic goods, such as organic apparel, is a result of expanding environmental sustainability consciousness. With an emphasis on retail establishments in Coimbatore, a well-known Indian city famous for its textile sector, this study explores customer awareness and attitudes towards organic apparel. The study investigates the elements that affect customer perception and purchasing decisions, looking at how well-informed consumers are about the advantages of organic apparel, including its positive effects on the environment, health, and ethical manufacturing methods. Consumers who visit Coimbatore retail stores were surveyed and interviewed to get data, and shops that sell organic apparel also provided insights. The results show that although some consumers are aware of organic apparel, there is still a large knowledge gap regarding its availability and complete advantages. Price, product quality, and brand reputation all have a significant influence on consumers' attitudes towards organic apparel; many still believe that organic clothing is pricey or hard to find.

1. INTRODUCTION

From the production of raw materials to the disposal of completed goods, the textile and apparel industries harm the environment at every stage of production. The textile industry's main environmental concerns are

chemical loading, excessive water and energy use, air pollution, solid waste, and odour production. Examining the textile industry's performance while taking the three sustainability components into account is essential to achieving sustainable production.

From an entrepreneurial perspective, environmental sustainability refers to a marketing strategy that uses methods that do not negatively impact the environment or natural resources during their life cycle (such as harvesting, producing, consuming, storing, and disposing of them).

For instance, these life cycle stages show how a cotton T-shirt affects the environment. Fertiliser, pesticides, and water are used in the growth of cotton; coal, dyes, and auxiliary materials, as well as water and electricity, are used in the dyeing and spinning of cotton; and power generation, washing, and liquid are used in the fabrication of T-shirts.

End users buy and use T-shirt items during consumption; during disposal, end users discard worn T-shirts and producers dispose of excess T-shirt manufacturing or material. The collection, processing, and application procedures are repeated to generate a reorder of T-shirts. Energy, chemicals, and water are therefore major environmental impact contributors in the manufacturing sector throughout the product life cycle. Clothing designers should use socially and ecologically conscious design principles and trends to ensure environmental sustainability; the supply chain should assess how their business activities affect the ecosystem, economy, and culture.

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess consumer awareness levels - regarding organic clothing and its benefits in Coimbatore retail outlets.
2. To analyze consumer attitudes and perceptions toward organic clothing - including preferences, willingness to pay, and sustainability concerns.

2. RELATED WORK

Roy Choudhury ^[1] Production technology used to meet expanding consumer demands, manufacturing activities have grown more important to the global environment. The growth of technology has resulted in environmental, air, and water degradation, ozone layer thinning, and a decline in green area. However, in response to these challenges, a sensitive public opinion has emerged, particularly in industrialized countries. New safeguards have started to be taken, both to sustain industrialization and to improve the environment.

Lee, K.E., ^[2] The major environmental effects of the textile industry include the discharge of large amounts of chemical loads due to the high consumption of water and harmful chemicals used in this industry. The corresponding water pollution, energy requirements in production processes and knowledge air emissions, packaging and waste management production issues, and the formation of toxic fumes caused by bleaching, dyeing, and printing procedures

Ahmed, S., Akter, T., Ma, Y., ^[3] Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM) strives to reduce environmental damage caused by industrial operations, thereby incorporating environmental concerns into supply chain management. Academics and practitioners alike have embraced the GSCM. The construction of a green supply chain has gained a lot of traction, and businesses in the textile sector are focusing more on increasing the visibility, efficiency.

Tesseract ^[5]

Tesseract is an optical character recognition engine, released under the apache licence. In 2006, it was considered to be one of the most accurate open source ocr engines.

The tesseract engine was released as open source by HP labs and the University of Nevada. Google has been sponsoring the development of tesseract since 2006. Tesseract can be executed via a command line interface.

It also has support for opening images using the leptonica ^[6] library.

Tesseract4 ^[7]

Tesseract4 uses a completely overhauled internal OCR engine. It uses a new neural network based recognition engine which enables it to deliver a significantly superior accuracy on document images than its predecessors.

However an increased accuracy comes at a tradeoff with a significant increase in the required compute power. The new engine helps deliver impressively accurate results even without manual enhancements of the images.

It has also shown capability in recognizing handwritten text.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research adopts a descriptive research design to analyze the impact of consumer cosmopolitanism on purchase intention and buying behavior for imported

and local electronic brands in Coimbatore City. The study is based on primary data, collected from 150 respondents using a simple random sampling technique to ensure unbiased representation. The research focuses on retail outlets in Coimbatore, providing insights into consumer preferences and buying patterns. To analyze the collected data, Chi-square and ANOVA test analyses are employed, enabling a comprehensive examination of the relationships between key variables.

4. FUTURE SCOPE AND CONCLUSION

The study highlights that while consumer awareness about organic clothing is growing in Coimbatore, there is still a need to strengthen market strategies and increase product availability. Price sensitivity remains a key factor influencing buying decisions. Effective awareness campaigns, competitive pricing, and improved product availability can drive higher adoption of organic clothing among consumers. Retailers can play a pivotal role by adopting eco-friendly practices and engaging with local producers to create a sustainable and profitable market for organic clothing. By addressing these factors, Coimbatore has the potential to enhance the market for organic clothing, businesses should focus on offering competitive pricing to make sustainable fashion more affordable and accessible. Additionally, implementing seasonal discounts and loyalty programs can help attract new customers and encourage repeat purchases. Educating consumers is also essential, and this can be achieved by training sales staff to effectively communicate the benefits of organic clothing. Moreover, providing support to retailers in sourcing and supply chain management will ensure a consistent supply of high-quality organic products. Collaborating with local organic cotton farmers and weavers not only strengthens the supply chain but also promotes sustainability and supports the local economy, creating a win-win situation for both producers and consumers.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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